

8T – The Bosonic Mass Pattern

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T and in particular the primordial coupling series, in the context of mass to massless Bosons, author makes a prediction regarding the Boson of the fourth coupling term, mass wise. Such a prediction is based upon a guess which is built upon a discrete jumps between mass positive and massless Bosons.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

So now instead of the classification of spin we can represent each coupling term to be a mixture of spins of distinct kind. Define spin operator:

$$\mathcal{L}: [\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{Q}] \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{[\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{Q}]} \quad (1.64)$$

That is a mapping between the integers and non-integer fields onto a spin operator in such way that the spin is matching the subscript:

$$\mathcal{L}: 0 \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_0$$

$$\mathcal{L}: \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{1/2}$$

$$\mathcal{L}: 1 \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_1$$

Now each coupling term can be represented in a way that reflect the idea of interacting fields, which are represented by spin operators.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_0 + \mathcal{S}_{1/2} + \mathcal{S}_1 \quad (1.44.A)$$

Let us analyze the idea of the mass pattern. The Boson of the first coupling term is described by one number, and we know its massless. The second coupling Bosons has a positive mass. The second coupling also differ by an additional term from the first coupling. The Boson of the third coupling, i.e. the photon, is again considered massless, even though it is a carrier of energy and can exert pressure. The subject of this paper is the following, can we predict a pattern in which the primordial coupling series generate mass. That is, is there a discrete jumps between massless to mass positive. Author is going to assume there is a mass pattern of that kind. Define the Boson mass by the parameter:

$$\mathcal{X}: M \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_M$$

The Gluon, W and Z Bosons and the photon has the relation according to the above operator:

$$\mathfrak{B}_{M=0}: \mathfrak{B}_{M>0}: \mathfrak{B}_{M=0}$$

The author will make a prediction that the fourth coupling term according to the primordial will possess a positive mass. That is the fourth coupling term will be described by $\mathfrak{B}_{M>0}$. By the ratio of the net variations of the fourth and the second, the fourth term is describing bigger Quanta than the Quanta of the Weak interaction. In particular, the mass of the fourth coupling term should be 2.1333 higher than the Masses of the Bosons of the weak interaction.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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